

Is Fermat's Principle Contained in $E = pc$?

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Fermat's minimal time principle involves extremizing total time traveled by light by assuming straight line motion in a medium and writing time = distance / speed. It may be applied to examples such as a stationary or constantly moving mirror (in the y direction) or refraction. As shown in (1) to extremize one must take a derivative of time with respect to an invariant spatial variable. This leads to a conservation law which is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the direction of the invariant spatial variable as argued in (1).

The wave dispersion relation velocity = frequency * wavelength may be written as $E=pc$ for a photon using Maxwell's equations and averaging. Next c may be written as x/t yielding: $A = 0 = -Et + px$ where $x/t = E/p = c$ (in a vacuum). In such a case dA/dx partial = p . For three dimensions, px is replaced with $px x + py y + pz z$. If x is the invariant variable as in reflection/refraction problems (which do not contain z) then dA/dx partial = px which is a conserved quantity (from Fermat's principle or first principles). If one does not use a partial derivative then: $0 = dA/dx = -E dt/dx + (px)$ where x is the invariant variable. For a refraction problem for which E is the same in both media: $0 = -E dt_1/dx + (p_1x) - E dt_2/dx + (p_2x)$. With conservation: $p_1x = p_2x$ one obtains Fermat's principle: $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$.

For a constantly moving mirror in the y direction matters are a little more complicated. E_1, p_1 and E_2, p_2 differ with the speed of light being c because there is one medium. V is the speed of the mirror in the negative y-direction. There, however, exist two relative speeds in the problem along the incident and reflected ray directions namely: $v(\text{relative a}) = c - v \cos(A)$ and $v(\text{relative b}) = c + v \cos(B)$ where A and B are the incident and reflected angles measured from the y-axis. If one uses $(E_1 \text{ special}) = p_1 v(\text{relative a})$ and a similar expression for p_2 then $(E_1 \text{ special})$ and $(E_2 \text{ special})$ are equal. There is still spatial invariance in the problem and $(E_1 \text{ special}) = p_1 (v(\text{relative a}))$ together with $(E_2 \text{ special}) = p_2 v(\text{relative b})$ is equivalent to Fermat's principle as will be shown.

Fermat's Principle

Fermat's principle involves extremizing time by writing it in terms of distance / light speed and varying an invariant spatial variable. The invariant spatial variable is chosen as one for which there is no discontinuity in the medium or mirror surface. For example if a mirror (stationary or moving) has a flat surface in the x direction and a medium surface is in the x direction, x is the invariant variable.

At first this seems to have nothing to do with momentum, but it seems momentum may change if there is a medium or mirror discontinuity and does not change if there is not one. Thus as we argued in (1) Fermat's principle is directly linked to conservation of momentum in the direction of spatial invariance.

To see that Fermat's principle is equivalent to a conservation law for a two ray problem (reflection from a stationary or constantly moving mirror in the y direction or refraction) one may note that for say refraction time = distance / (c/n) where n is the index of refraction. Distance is given by: $\sqrt{YY + xx}$ and $\sqrt{YY + (L-x)(L-x)}$ where the same absolute value of Y is used for

both rays and L is an x parameter in keeping with this with x being the point at which the incident ray hits the medium. X does not have a medium discontinuity because the medium surface is in the x direction. Thus it is an invariant variable. Then:

$$0 = dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = n_1 x / \{c \text{ hypotenuse}(1)\} - n_2 (L-x) / \{c \text{ hypotenuse } 2 \}$$

$$\rightarrow n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 \sin(B) \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is of the form of a conservation law, but does not explicitly contain momentum. If $E=pc$ and E is the same in both media, then $c \rightarrow c/n$ means $p \rightarrow pn$ and one may multiply ((1)) by a constant such that it is directly equivalent to:

$$P_1 \sin(A) = p_1 x = p_2 \sin(B) = p_2 x \quad ((2))$$

Thus Fermat's principle is equivalent to a conservation law due to an invariant variable which in turn is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the direction of the invariant variable. A moving mirror problem is very similar, but n_1 is replaced with $1/v(\text{relative } a)$ and n_2 with $1/v(\text{relative } b)$ where $v(\text{relative } a) = c - v \cos(A)$ and $v(\text{relative } b) = c + v \cos(B)$. There is again a conservation law and it is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the x direction, but one cannot use $E=pc$ because c is the vacuum speed of light, rather there is a number E special such that $E \text{ special} = p_1 v(\text{relative } a)$ with $p_1 = \text{constant} / v(\text{relative } a)$ so that $E_a (\text{special})$ is the same as $E_b \text{ special}$). We shall show this explicitly later in the note.

Thus the main point we wish to make is that Fermat's principle for two ray problems is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the direction of an invariant variable (usually taken to be the x variable.). As a result, if one were to try to reformulate Fermat's principle one would need an expression which contains t (because one takes dt/dx) and a term $(px) x$ to obtain the conserved quantity. We suggest that such an expression may be $E=pc$ the usual photon dispersion result.

E=pc

The common wave relationship:

$$\text{Velocity} = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength} \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{may be adjusted for a photon to yield: } c \text{ (speed of light)} p \text{ (momentum)} = E \text{ (energy)} \quad ((4))$$

This follows from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations with averaging. If one write speed of light = c (vacuum) = x/t then:

$$A = 0 = -Et + px \quad \text{or more generally } A = 0 = -Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z \quad \text{with } c=r/t \quad ((5))$$

This is in the form of the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which is the argument of $\cos(-Et+px)$ which when multiplied by a constant describes the changing electric field of the photon.

((5)) we argue seems to contain Fermat's principle implicitly. One must choose the invariant spatial variable, say x , and then take d/dx assuming $t(x)$. The invariant variable is one for which there does not exist a medium discontinuity. For example in the case of a stationary or constantly moving mirror in the y direction or refraction with the medium surface along x , discontinuity occurs in the y direction. (Only x and y directions exist in these problems.) From ((5))

$$\text{Ray 1 } -E_1 dt_1/dx + (p_1 x) = 0 \quad \text{and Ray 2 } -E_2 dt_2/dx + (p_2 x) = 0$$

If $E_1=E_2$ as it does for refraction and $p_1 x = p_2 x$ i.e conservation of momentum in the direction of the invariant variable then:

$dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$ ((6)) which is Fermat's principle (for the $E_1=E_2$ case i.e. refraction as an example).

The Case of a Constantly Moving Mirror in the y direction

Consider reflection from a mirror moving with speed v in the negative y direction. In such a case there is an incident E_1, p_1 (vector) and reflected E_2, p_2 (vector) with E_1 not equal to E_2 . Furthermore the speed of light c is the same because there is only one medium. Fermat's principle still involves $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$ and is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the x direction. Simply applying Fermat's principle (with no notion of momentum) yields (2):

$$\sin(A) / v(\text{relative } a) = \sin(B) / v(\text{relative } b) \quad ((7))$$

where $v(\text{relative } a) = c - v \cos(A)$ and $v(\text{relative } b) = c + v \cos(B)$.

How may one link ((7)) to $-Et+ p \cdot r$? We suggest introducing a hypothetical energy E special such that:

$$E \text{ special} = p v(\text{relative } i) \quad ((8))$$

Applying this to the reflection from a moving mirror problem yields:

$$0 = dt_1/dx (E_1 \text{ special}) + (p_1 x) + dt_2/dx (E_2 \text{ special}) + (p_2 x)$$

$(p_1 x) = (p_2 x)$ because there is no discontinuity of medium in the x direction. Thus one requires that $E_1 \text{ special} = E_2 \text{ special}$. From ((7))

$$\sin(A) p_1 / (E_1 \text{ special}) = \sin(B) p_2 / (E_2 \text{ special}) \quad ((9))$$

$p_1 \sin(A)$, however, equals $p_2 \sin(B)$ by conservation of momentum in the x direction so:

$$E_1 \text{ special} = E_2 \text{ special} \quad ((10))$$

Thus there exists a special E such that the photon dispersion relationship may be written as ((8)) with E special being the same for the incident and reflected rays (for a moving mirror) just as regular E is the same for the incident and refracted rays. Thus the moving mirror problem also seems to be incorporated within an $E = p$ velocity equation; it is just that E and velocity are not the usual photon E and c or c/n .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the wave dispersion relationship for a photon i.e. $E=pc$ seems to contain Fermat's least time principle implicitly. In (1) we argued that Fermat's principle which involves extremizing time with respect to an invariant spatial variable leads to a conservation law in the direction of this same variable which is equivalent to conservation of momentum in this direction. Thus it seems that Fermat's principle should be equivalent to an expression involving t and $p \cdot r$. We suggest that this expression is $A=0 = -Et + (p_x)x + (p_y)y + (p_z)z$ with c speed of light being r/t and $t(x)$. For two rays one has (taking dt/dx where x is the spatially invariant variable: $-E_1 dt_1/dx + (p_1)_x - E_2 dt_2/dx + (p_2)_x = 0$. With $p_1)_x = p_2)_x$ and $E_1 = E_2$ one has: $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$ which is Fermat's principle. Such an approach holds for refraction for which $E_1 = E_2$. The spatially invariant variable is chosen such that there is no medium discontinuity in direction of the variable. For reflection from a stationary mirror or one moving with constant speed in the negative y direction or refraction with the medium surface along x, x is the invariant variable.

For the case of a constantly moving mirror in the negative y direction, there is again invariance in x and conservation of momentum in the x direction. The problem is that E_1 does not equal E_2 in particular there is a distinct E_1 , p_1 vector for the incident ray and another E_2 , p_2 vector for the reflected. One may bypass this problem, however, and still retain the wave dispersion relationship by postulating:

$$E \text{ special} = p v(\text{relative } i) \quad \text{where } v(\text{relative incident}) = c - v \cos(A) \text{ and } v(\text{relative reflected}) = c + v \cos(B)$$

A and B are incident and reflected angles measured from y. We have shown above from the results of Fermat's principle that $E_1 \text{ special} = E_2 \text{ special}$, thus a wave dispersion relationship is again equivalent to Fermat's principle, but one must adjust the speed and energy in the relationship.

References

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